

THE GROWTH AND YIELD RESPONSE OF LETTUCE (*Lactuca sativa* L.) AS AFFECTED BY DIFFERENT SOURCES OF FOLIAR FERTILIZER

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Abstract

Due to increasing population there is a need to increase food production and one of the common methods to increase production is the use of chemical fertilizers for fast crop growth without even thinking the adverse effects it may have to people. In response to this, Republic Act 10068 Organic Agriculture Act of 2010 an act that provides safe food for the people and ensure sustainability of the environment. The study aims to determine the effect of different foliar fertilizer derived from different sources. The following treatments were evaluated; Control water only (T0), Extract from fruit scraps (T1), Extract from vegetable scraps (T2), Extract from leftover rice (T3), and Extract from mixed scrap of fruits, vegetable and leftover rice (T4). Collected foliar fertilizer solutions from the different food scraps were subjected for NPK analysis. Foliar extract from leftover rice (T3) obtained the highest total NPK content of 0.67%. Results of pot experiment for the efficacy of the different collected foliar showed that foliar fertilizer obtained from mixed scraps (T4) increased the plant height, obtained bigger size of leaves and consequently obtained the heaviest weight.

Keywords: Organic Agriculture; Foliar Fertilizer; Plant Height; Number of Leaves Per Plant; Length of Leaves; Weight of Plant; NPK.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Ten years ago, there were 2.9 billion urban residents who generated about 0.64 kg of municipal solid waste (MSW) per person per day which is equivalent to 0.68 billion tons per year. The report estimates that the amounts have increased to about 3 billion residents generating 1.2 kg per person per day or equivalent to 1.3 billion tons per year and by 2025 this will likely increase to 4.3 billion. However, poorly managed waste has enormous impacts especially on health, local and global environment, and economy (Hoornweg & Bhada-Tata, 2012). In order to lessen the above issue, segregation of wastes was mandated under Republic Act 9003 or the Ecological Solid Waste Management so that all biodegradable waste can be converted into organic fertilizer that can be used in crop production.

The Philippine government formulated the Republic Act 10068, aims to strengthen the state's policy to promote the practice of organic agriculture. Organic farming enriches the fertility of the soil, increases farm productivity, reduces pollution and destruction of the environment, prevents depletion of natural resources, protects the health of the farmers and the public (Prado & Sampaga, 2013). Hence, organic agriculture is formed to manage or lessen the utilization of synthetic chemicals that imposed negative impacts to the environment. Organic fertilizers generally contain lower NPK and releases nutrients at a slower rate compared to synthetic fertilizers. It offers a healthier alternative to chemical fertilizers, it rejuvenate and sustained

soil fertility. Composting is a process or method that produces products like organic fertilizer. Composting processes in a tropical climate with a dry season like the Philippines is possible and which can obtain a good quality organic fertilizer in less than three months that makes more production (Maso & Blasi, 2008). There are many kinds of solid and liquid organic fertilizers, namely; vermicast, fermented fruits and vegetables, fish amino acid, lactic acid serum and bokashi. They also mentioned that Bokashi composting is a very quick process. The primary component in bokashi compost is food waste which produces liquid fertilizer that can be used as foliar fertilizer to supplement the nutrient requirement of the crop (Fageria et al., 2017). Hence, production of foliar fertilizer utilizing biodegradable wastes will help reduced the wastes being dump in the landfills.

METHODOLOGY

Phase 1: Production of Foliar Fertilizer

Collection of Raw Materials for the Preparation of Foliar Fertilizer

Two kilograms of each biodegradable materials (fruit scraps, vegetables scraps, and leftover rice) were collected from food stalls within the University campus and at men's dormitories. The EM inoculant, molasses and rice bran were bought at Agricultural supply store. After the collection, all collected food wastes were brought immediately to the RM-CARES material recovery facility for fermentation process.

Preparation of Bokashi Bran

EM bokashi was prepared by mixing 88.7 mL molasses, 3.8 liters of water and 88.7 mL EM inoculant then poured into the 5.44 kg rice bran in a closed container. Anaerobic fermentation occurred in the closed container under a temperature ranging from 20-40°C within 2-3 weeks.

Preparation of Different Treatments as Source of Foliar Fertilizer

Preparations of different treatments for the source of foliar fertilizer was done in a plastic container by putting the different food scrap separately in each of the container by layering 1 kilo of food scrap (fresh fruits, vegetables, leftover rice) plus 1 kilogram of bokashi bran. Each set-up was covered with plastic in order to prevent air from entering during fermentation and were pressed from time to time during fermentation. The extracts of the different set-ups were collected after 14 days.

Treatments

The following treatments for the source of foliar fertilizer were established:

Treatment 1: 1 kg fruits scraps + 1 kg bokashi bran

Treatment 2: 1 kg vegetables scraps + 1 kg bokashi bran

Treatment 3: 1 kg leftover rice + 1 kg bokashi bran

Treatment 4: 0.33 g mixture of fruits, 0.33 g vegetables, 0.33 g leftover rice + 1 kg bokashi bran

Nutrient Analysis of the Foliar Fertilizer

After the collection of different liquid solutions, 300 ml sample of each extract were separately collected and put in a bottle for the analysis of Nutrient content. The samples were submitted to the Regional Soil Laboratory in San Fernando, Pampanga for NPK determination.

Phase 2: Efficacy Testing

Efficacy of the different foliar derived from the different sources were tested, efficacy trial was conducted in a pot experiment, the experiment was established in a screen house of the RM-CARES office.

Test Crop

Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) romaine variety was the test crop for this particular experiment. This variety was chosen for this particular study because it was proven and tested under pure organic system. This variety matures from 30-45 days.

Potting Media

Before transplanting the experimental crop, potting media was prepared by mixing one part of carbonized rice hull plus one part of organic fertilizer (1:1 ratio). The mixed potting media was put in a black polyethylene with a size of 12 x 11 inches. Each polyethylene bags contained 8kg of the potting media.

Treatments

The following treatments were evaluated for the efficacy of the different foliar fertilizer.

T0 = Control (Water Only)

T1= Juice extract from fruit scraps at the rate of 100 ml/1 liter of water

T2= Juice extract from vegetable scraps at the rate of 100 ml/1 liter of water

T3= Juice extract from leftover rice at the rate of 100 ml/1 liter of water

T4= Juice extract from mixed fruit scraps, vegetable scraps, leftover rice and bread at the rate of 100 ml/1 liter of water

Seedling Production

Lettuce seeds were planted on seedling trays with the mixture of carbonized rice hull and organic fertilizer as the potting media at a ratio of 1:1. Seeds were planted in every hole with at a depth of 0.5 cm with one seeds per hole. Regulated watering was done to avoid excessive moisture and to prevent possible attack of microorganisms like bacteria and fungi.

Hardening

Before transplanting, hardening of seedling was done by exposing the two week old seedlings to sunlight. This was done for 5 days until the seedlings were ready for transplanting.

Transplanting

The seedlings were transplanted 3 weeks after seed sowing in a prepared pots by planting 4 seedlings in each pot. Planting was done late in the afternoon to avoid wilting of the seedlings during day time.

Treatment Application

Initial application of foliar fertilizer was done 3 days after transplanting. Application method was done using hand spraying and was applied once a day. Succeeding application was done at 5 days interval. Four applications were applied until harvesting.

Care and Management of Plant

Water Management

Watering of the experimental crops was done regularly to maintained the soil moisture and avoid wilting of the experimental crop. Watering was done twice a day, 1 liter of water early in the morning and 1 liter in the late afternoon.

Pest and Disease Management

Control of insect pest and diseases was done by regular monitoring of the experimental crop. No infestation or occurrence of insect pests and disease was observed during the whole duration of the experiment.

Weed Management

Experimental pots were maintained by pulling the germinated weeds. This was done regularly throughout the whole duration of the observation.

Data Gathered

1. NPK Analysis

This was done by taking samples of different extract. The sample were brought to the Regional Soil Laboratory for the determination of NPK content. The sample bottles were covered with aluminum foil in order to protect the microorganisms present from the direct exposure to sunlight.

2. Plant Height (cm)

Plant height was taken from the 9 sample plants in each replications. Measurement was done from the ground level up to the highest tip of the leaves using a ruler.

3. Width of Leaves (cm)

Width of the leaves was taken from 5 individual leaves (2 at the bottom, 2 at the middle and 1 at the top) from the 9 sample plants. Measurement was done on the widest portion of leaf using a ruler.

4. Length of Leaves (cm)

Length of leaves was taken from the 5 individual leaves. Sample leaves were taken from the bottom, middle at the top portion of the plant were measured measurement was done the base of the petiole up to the tip of the leaf blade using a ruler.

5. Number of Leaves per Plant

Number of leaves was taken by counting all the leaves of plants except for the dried/dead leaves. This was taken from the 9 sample plants from each replications.

6. Weight of Plant

Weight of plants was done by weighing the individual plants harvested in each treatment using digital weighing scale.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Produced Foliar Fertilizer

Table 3 shows the characteristics of harvested foliar and the NPK analysis from the different sources, result of the laboratory analysis showed that foliar from burnt rice obtained the highest total NPK of 0.67% with 0.42% N, 0.16% P and 0.09% K while foliar from fruits and vegetable scraps obtained a total NPK of 0.45% and 0.47%, respectively.

Table 3: NPK content of the foliar fertilizer from various food scraps

Foliar Fertilizer Source	Foliar Characteristics			pH	% (N)	% (P2O5)	% (K2O)
	Visual description	Odor	Color				
Fruit scraps (T1)	Liquid	none	Light orange	5.36	0.11	0.16	0.18
Vegetable scraps (T2)	Liquid	none	Light orange	6.76	0.12	0.09	0.21
Burnt Rice (T3)	Liquid	none	Orange	5.59	0.42	0.16	0.09
Mixed scraps (T4)	Liquid	none	Slightly dark orange	5.54	0.13	0.16	0.15

In terms of pH, foliar from vegetable scrap (T2) obtained the highest pH of 6.76 compared to other treatments. This could be due to the substrates used which are watery unlike the other substrates which are little bit dried or minimal water are present. Lind (2014) stated in his study that the nutrient content in leachate or juice may vary depending on the source of the food waste or scraps. Fruit scrap (T1), leftover rice (T3) and Mixed scrap (T4) obtained lower pH level because of the Lactic Acid Bacteria (LAB) present in the EM solution, as supported by the study of Footer (2014) which states that LAB can decrease the pH level during the fermentation process.

In terms of nitrogen content, leftover rice (T3) obtained the highest percentage of Nitrogen (0.42%) due to the rice substrate which is a good source of nitrogen. It was stated in the Przulji, R. & Momcilovic, V. (2001) that during the maturity of rice, 75% of nitrogen is assimilated to the grains. In that case, during decomposition inside the bin it produces ammonia that later on nitrifies and produces available nitrate for the plant to absorb.

In terms of phosphorus, vegetable scraps (T2) obtained the lowest phosphorus content due to the substrates which are low in phosphorus such as bitter melon (*Momordica charantia L.*) bottle gourd (*Lagenaria siceraria*), carrots (*Daucus carota*) etc. Meanwhile, T1, T3 and T4 obtained similar percentage of phosphorus. According Patil (2011), that foods rich in proteins were also rich in phosphorus like leftover rice (T3) however molasses and fruits also contain phosphorus such as banana (*Musa sp.*).

Meanwhile, vegetable scraps (T2) obtained the highest potassium content because the presence of the potato scraps (*Solanum tuberosum*). This results conforms to the result of study of Chandrashekhar, V. (2019) that potatoes are good source of potassium having 541 mg. Meanwhile fruits scraps (T1) obtained 0.18% potassium due to the presence of the banana (*Musa sp.*) scraps and he mentioned that banana (*Musa sp.*) was also rich in potassium.

Plant Height

Plant height of lettuce at harvest as affected by the application of different treatments was presented in Table 4. Results showed that plants applied with foliar from mixed scraps (T4) significantly obtained the tallest plant height of 27cm. According to El-zabalawy, K., Mustafa, A. and Elbanna, B. (2017) applying foliar can improve soil condition that favor plant growth. Christel (2017), stated that mixed foliar treatment had the greatest concentration of NO₃--N nutrient that is available for plant adsorption, resulting to positive effect on crop growth.

Table 4: Average plant height (cm) as affected by the application of different sources of foliar fertilizer

Treatment	Replication				
	I	II	III	Total	Mean
Control (T0)	21.00	21.00	21.75	63.75	21.25 ^b
Fruit scraps(T1)	23.00	21.25	22.50	67.00	22.25 ^b
Vegetable scraps(T2)	23.50	22.25	19.5	65.25	21.75 ^b
Leftover Rice(T3)	24.30	23.83	20.00	68.13	22.71 ^b
Mixed scraps (T4)	35.75	23.50	21.75	81.00	27.00 ^a

* Means followed by the same letter(s) superscript are not significantly different at 5%.

* CV 7.34 %

Analysis of variance (Appendix Table 1) showed that plants applied with, fruit scraps (T1), vegetable scraps (T2) and leftover rice (T3) and the control (T0) plants significantly obtained comparable plant height with 22.25 cm, 21.75 cm, 22.71 cm and 21.25 cm, respectively. According to Discartin, J. and Ventura, E. (2014) combination of fermented fruit juice, fermented plant juice with Vermicast and oriental herbal nutrient was observed to have improved plant height of Lettuce (*Lactuca sativa L.*). In this case single substrate application like rice, vegetable and fruits alone didn't release enough growth promotant compared to T4 mixed which is a combination of the food scraps (rice, vegetable and fruits).

Width of Leaves

In terms of width of leaves, no significant differences among the different treatments applied were obtained. Application of different extract did not affect the leaves formation Table 5. The result could be supported by the findings Yamada, K. and Xu, H., (2008) that application of the EM did not affect plant growth due to fluctuation of environmental conditions such as temperature of the surroundings and transpiration. According to Accuweather (2018) high temperature can affect the growth of lettuce plant because this kind of plant is produced or grown in cold places with a temperature of 60-70°F (15-20°C) to meet its optimum growth. Ojeda, A. and Ligarreto, G. (2012) states that high temperatures 24°C above can cause significant changes in the endosperm layer and produce large changes in the morphology of the plant.

Table 5: Average width (cm) of leaves as affected by the application different sources of foliar fertilizer

Treatment	Replication				
	I	II	III	Total	Mean
Control (T0)	11.93	11.55	10.05	33.63	11.17
Fruit scraps(T1)	11.50	11.40	10.80	33.70	11.23
Vegetable scraps(T2)	11.80	10.20	10.70	32.70	10.90
Leftover Rice(T3)	12.00	10.60	10.40	33.00	11.00
Mixed scraps (T4)	12.20	11.80	11.00	35.00	11.66

* Means followed by the same letter(s) superscript are not significantly different at 5%.

* CV 4.01%

Length of Leaves

Length of leaves as affected by the application of different treatment was shown in Table 6. Results show that plants applied with extract from mixed scraps (T4) significantly obtained the longest leaves of 14.29 cm followed by plants applied with extract from leftover rice (T3) with an average length of 14.03cm this could be due to the available nitrogen absorbed by the plants hence these two treatments obtained the highest nitrogen content. This result could be supported by the findings Mukhtar, M. and Astawa, I. (2015), that in order to boost the vegetative growth of a plant, it is required to apply nitrogen. In addition to this the study of Vera (2012) stated that a good supply of nitrogen is associated with high photosynthetic activity causing healthy vegetative growth.

Analysis of variance (Appendix Table 5) showed that comparable length of leaves was obtained by the control plants (T0) and those plants applied with vegetable scraps (T2) with 13.27 cm and 13.17cm, respectively. Since the data was gathered at harvest T0 and T2 reach its maturity even before its harvest period come. Hence, when a plant reaches its maturity plant growth will start to slow down. The shortest length of leaves was obtained from the plants applied with the extract from fruits scraps (T1) with 13.07 cm. This could be due to the fact that fruit extract contain very low NPK especially nitrogen as shown in Table 3 which is required to boost the vegetative growth of a plant.

Table 6: Average length (cm) of leaves as affected by the application different sources of foliar fertilizer

Treatment	Replication				
	I	II	III	Total	Mean
Control (T0)	13.30	13.10	13.40	39.80	13.27 bc
Fruit scraps(T1)	13.80	12.00	13.40	39.20	13.07 c
Vegetable scraps(T2)	13.40	13.40	12.70	39.50	13.17 bc
Leftover Rice(T3)	14.55	13.40	14.13	42.08	14.03 ab
Mixed scraps (T4)	14.46	14.20	14.20	42.86	14.29 a

* Means followed by the same letter(s) superscript are not significantly different at 5%.

* CV 3.42 %

Average Number of Leaves

The average number of leaves produced per plant applied with the different treatments was shown in Table 7. Results shows that plant applied with extract from leftover rice (T3) obtained the most number of leaves per plant with 9.89 leaves. This could be due to the amount of nitrogen present in the leachate or juice because during maturity, 75% of nitrogen assimilated to the grains. In this case in order for the plants to uptake this nutrient, rice was fermented which produced ammonia and by the process of nitrification inside the bin the nitrogen in leftover rice turned into nitrate that can be taken up by plants. Hence in the study of Agustin (2009) Greater amount of nitrogen helps boost the photosynthetic activity of the lettuce plant resulting to production of more food that is used in physiological processes needed for growth and development, thereby causing more leaves. Also based on the result of study conducted by Wijayanto, M. et al. (2016) the use of bokashi on soybean significantly affects the increase of number of leaves.

Statically (Appendix Table 5), it is comparable with the number of leaves produced with those plants applied with extract from fruit scraps (T1), vegetable scraps (T2), leftover rice (T3) and mixed scrap (T4) with 9.17, 9.00 and 9.31, respectively. The lowest number of leaves produced per plant was obtained in the control group T0 with a value of 7.05 leaves.

Table 7: Average number of leaves produced per plant as affected by the application of different sources of foliar fertilizer

Treatment	Replication				
	I	II	III	Total	Mean
Control (T0)	6.50	6.66	8.00	21.16	7.05 b
Fruit scraps(T1)	10.00	9.00	8.50	27.50	9.17 a
Vegetable scraps(T2)	9.50	8.50	9.00	27.00	9.00 a
Leftover Rice(T3)	10.66	9.00	10.00	29.66	9.89 a
Mixed scraps (T4)	10.00	9.33	8.60	27.93	9.31 a

* Means followed by the same letter(s) superscript are not significantly different at 5%.

* CV 7.59%

Weight of Plant

The weight of harvested plant as affected by the application of different treatments was shown in Table 8. Results showed that plant applied with extract from mixed scrap (T4) significantly obtained the heaviest weight of 63.92 g. This happened because of the combined nutrients from mixed scraps which produced enough nutrients in order to absorb the plants. Likewise, the results confirm the findings of Christel (2017) that application of foliar fertilizer in spinach has greater marketable yield. Also it's stated that application of mixed foliar resulted to heavier lettuce heads. On the other hand, based on the analysis, mixed foliar has contain almost similar NPK content which contributed to the gain in weight at harvest.

Table 8: Average weight per plant (g) as affected by the application different sources of foliar fertilizer

Treatment	Replication				
	I	II	III	Total	Mean
Control (T0)	43.60	39.05	55.90	138.55	46.18 d
Fruit scraps(T1)	63.53	47.15	51.05	161.73	53.91 c
Vegetable scraps(T2)	61.10	57.30	49.45	167.85	55.95 c
Leftover Rice(T3)	66.50	54.25	59.30	180.05	59.68 b
Mixed scraps (T4)	69.00	69.75	55.00	193.75	63.92 a

* Means followed by the same letter(s) superscript are not significantly different at 5%.

* CV 9.90%

Vegetable scraps (T2) and fruit scraps (T1) obtained a comparable weight of 55.95 g and 53.91g, respectively. This means that the nutrients from these treatments had the same effects to the plant because of lack of nitrogen content based on the analysis. And also as stated in the study of Agustin (2009), more amount of nitrogen is needed in order to produce more food that can be used in physiological processes necessary for the growth and development of the plant thereby generating more leaves and heavy weight which contributes to higher yield.

The lowest weight was obtained by the control plant with 46.18g. Moreover, according to Fageria, N. et al. (2017) essential plant nutrients like in foliar fertilizer when applied can contribute to maximum economic yield. In addition to this Christel, (2017) said in her study on spinach applied with foliar fertilizer significantly obtained greater marketable yield than all other treatments.

Total Weight/ Yield

In terms of yield, harvested yield per pot Table 9 shows that application of extract from leftover rice (T3) obtained the highest yield of 142.20g and Suthamathy, N. and Seran, T. (2013), mentioned that in the study of Higa (1988) this could be due to population of photosynthetic bacteria and nitrogen fixing bacteria dramatically increased and is associated to higher plant yield and quality. However, statistically, leftover rice (T3) and mixed scrap (T4) significantly obtained comparable yield of 142.20 g and 141.50 g, respectively.

Table 9: Total weight (g) of harvested plant as affected by the application of different sources of foliar fertilizer

Treatment	Replication				
	I	II	III	Total	Mean
Control (T0)	130.80	78.10	111.80	320.70	106.09 d
Fruit scraps(T1)	102.10	94.30	190.60	387.00	129.00 c
Vegetable scraps(T2)	114.60	183.30	98.90	396.80	132.27 b
Leftover Rice(T3)	199.50	108.50	118.60	426.60	142.20 a
Mixed scraps (T4)	90.00	196.50	138.00	424.50	141.50 a

* Means followed by the same letter(s) superscript are not significantly different at 5%.

* CV 1.18%

The control plant obtained the lowest yield of 106.09 g. because it only gets its nutrients in the potting media itself due to no supplement of nutrients added compared to the other treatments. In the study of Mayer, J., Scheid, S., Widmer, F., Fliebach, A., & Oberholzer, H. (2010), said that Effective Microorganism Activated (EMA) spraying combined with foliar fertilizer increased wheat yields compared to untreated control.

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